

DEPOLYMERISATION OF POST-CONSUMER PET BOTTLES WITH AMINOLYSIS IN THE PRESENCE OF ORGANOCATALYST

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Abstract: Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) is a saturated polyester synthesized by the esterification of a dibasic acid (terephthalic acid) and a diol (ethylene glycol) and is used for fibres, bottles, films, and other moulded products. PET is recycled by both physical and chemical routes. The physical route generally consists of remelting and forming new products with the help of suitable additives. PET can be chemically reprocessed by complete depolymerisation into oligomers, monomers, and other by-products. In this way, a wide range of terephthalamide monomers can be produced, which can serve as building blocks for high-performance materials with desired mechanical and thermal properties. In this study, different amines (ethylenediamine - EDA, 1,4-diaminobutane - DAB, 1,6-diaminohexane - DAH) were used to depolymerise post-consumer PET beverage bottles. The bottles were cut into pieces with an edge length of less than 2 cm. Aminolysis of PET was carried out in the presence of organocatalyst (1,5,7-triazabicyclo[4.4.0]dec-5-ene (TBD)) and with an excess of amine (ethylenediamine, 1,4-diaminobutane, 1,6-diaminohexane; 1.5 and 3 eq.). After completion of the reaction the product was isolated, washed with organic solvents and dried. The products bearing amino functional groups were characterised by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC).

Keywords: PET bottles, aminolysis, depolymerisation, chemical recycling

1 INTRODUCTION

Poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) is one of the most widely used thermoplastics in various applications, such as packaging, textiles, and engineering. However, the increasing production and consumption of PET also pose significant environmental challenges, especially regarding the disposal and recycling of PET waste. Mechanical recycling, the predominant method of recycling PET, has several limitations, such as deterioration of material properties, contamination by other polymers or additives, and accumulation of waste in landfills.(Brivio & Tollini, 2022; Schyngs & Shaver, 2021) Chemical recycling, which depolymerises PET into its monomers or other valuable chemicals, offers an alternative and potentially more sustainable way of recovering pure material and reducing environmental impact.(Shojaei et al., 2020) However, chemical recycling also faces technical and economic barriers such as high energy consumption, low efficiency, and lack of market competitiveness.

One of the promising methods of chemical recycling is aminolysis, which is the reaction of PET with amines to produce terephthalamides.(Ghosal & Nayak, 2022; Gupta & Bhandari, 2019; Zhou et al., 2017) Terephthalamides are useful compounds that can be used as additives, modifiers, and building blocks for high performance materials, such as polyamides, polyimides, and polyurethanes. Terephthalamides have enhanced mechanical and thermal properties due to hydrogen bonding and rigidity of structure. Currently, most terephthalamides are prepared from dimethyl terephthalate (DMT) or terephthaloyl chloride (TC), which are the monomers of PET. However, using waste PET as a source of terephthalamides can potentially alleviate existing environmental concerns and positively impact the management of limited petroleum sources.

Aminolysis of PET is thermodynamically more favorable than alcoholysis, which is another common method of depolymerisation. However, aminolysis still requires catalysts or microwave irradiation to achieve efficient depolymerisation. In this paper, we report a novel organocatalytic aminolysis of PET using 1,5,7-triazabicyclo[4.4.0]dec-5-ene (TBD) as a potent and versatile catalyst. We demonstrate that TBD can effectively depolymerise PET under mild conditions and produce various terephthalamides with different amines.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Post-consumer PET bottles and PET recyclates were used as the PET source. The bottles were washed, dried, and shredded by hand to a size of about 4-6 cm².

PET recycle and PET flakes were dried at 80°C under vacuum overnight prior to use.

2. 2 PET depolymerisation via aminolysis

The depolymerisation of PET (Figure 1) was performed using ethylenediamine EDA, DAB and DAH with excess of amine (4 and 8 mol eq.). TBD was used as catalyst.

Figure 1. Scheme for PET depolymerisation via aminolysis.

PET flakes were placed into a 50 ml flask with excess amounts of ethylenediamine (4 or 8 mol eq.) and TBD (0.05 mol eq.). The flask was then heated under nitrogen atmosphere at 110°C for 90 min. The solution was then poured into 50 ml of hot toluene and filtered. The residue was dissolved in methanol and the filtrate was evaporated. The residue was washed with isopropanol and dried in a vacuum oven at 80°C, yielding a white powdery product.

The aminolysis, which was carried out with 4 mol eq. of amine, did not proceed with any of the amines used. Even when the reaction time was extended to 180 min, the reaction did not proceed. The conversions of the aminolysis with 8 mol eq. of amine are shown in Figure 2. As can be seen from the Figure 2, the conversion obtained depends on the amine chosen, being lowest for EDA (61.1 %) and slightly higher for DAB (82.1 %). In the case of DAH, the conversion was over 100 %, which is due to the presence of the unreacted amine.

Figure 2. Conversions (%) of PET as a function of used amine (EDA, DAB, DAH). Aminolysis was conducted with 8 mol eq. of amine.

2. 3 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

In this study, terephthalamides obtained from organocatalytic aminolysis of PET were characterised by FTIR. The FTIR spectra of the samples were recorded using a PerkinElmer Spectrum 65 spectrometer equipped with a universal attenuated total reflectance (ATR) accessory. Spectra were recorded in the range $4000 - 600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and 32 scans per sample. The spectra were analysed using Spectrum software from PerkinElmer. The spectra (Figure 3) of the terephthalamides were compared with those of the starting materials PET flakes and the corresponding amines to confirm the formation of the amide bonds (1620 cm^{-1}) and the disappearance of the ester bonds (1714 cm^{-1}). The absorption band at 1714 cm^{-1} was assigned to the -C=O stretching of -COO- , the peak at 1095 cm^{-1} to the C-O trans vibration and the peak at 723 cm^{-1} to the out-of-plane C-H bending vibration of benzene. Compared to the spectrum of the PET flakes, the spectrum of the aminolyzed PET products contained new absorption peaks at 1540 cm^{-1} (in-plane -NH_2 scissoring), 655 cm^{-1} (-NH_2 out-of-plane wagging), 1620 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch). In addition, the amine (-NH_2) peaks are observed at $3440\text{--}3350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Figure 3. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra of samples.

2. 4 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

In our study DSC (Mettler Toledo, TGA/DSC 3+) was used to determine the melting point of the aminolysis product and the T_g, melting and crystallization of PET. Cold crystallization temperature for PET flakes was determined to be 149.9°C and melting point 246.2°C (the heating rate was 20°C/min and the N₂ flow was 20 mL/min). The melting points of the aminolysis products were in the range of 170 – 179°C, indicating terephthalamides.

3 CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated effective organocatalysis to promote aminolytic depolymerisation of PET flakes using TBD as a catalyst. Ethylenediamine, 1,4-diaminobutane and 1,6-diaminohexane were used as amines and terephthalamides were formed, which have great potential as building blocks due to their physical properties.

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